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(In)visibilized?

Roma in social, family, and workfare policy discourses in the authoritarian neoliberal context of Hungary

Pre-print

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Abstract

Purpose: This article explores how a disadvantaged ethnic minority is portrayed in government discourses related to social, family, and workfare policies in an illiberal and authoritarian neoliberal system, using the case of Hungary and Hungarian Roma. In our paper, relying on the theory of post-raciality and, within this, the concepts of (in)visibilization, we aim to reveal to what extent Roma are perceived as the undeserving racialized poor.

Design/methodology/approach: We deployed the policy frame analysis method to categorize policy discourse content into different frames: *diagnostic* (identification of the problem), *prognostic* (solutions to problems), and *motivational* (incentives for action to mobilize people). Three data sources were used: pro-government media articles, state-of-the-nation address speeches, and the party manifesto of the governing party. The timeframe of the analysis was between 2010 and 2023. The dataset consisted of 75 documents.

Findings: Only in a few cases did we find racializing language, typically at the beginning of the analyzed period, which gradually disappeared from the discourse, followed by a more paternalistic tone. We conclude that the notions of merit and self-responsibilization have been successfully used to hide (invisibilize) the structural causes of ethnic inequalities and shift the responsibility to individual efforts. The most vulnerable Roma, who are excluded from the labor market are perceived as not accepting the neoliberal and paternalistic ‘social contract’. At the same time, they are made invisible by being omitted from the official narrative.

Originality/value: A wide range of literature tackles questions like how neoliberal authoritarianism is related to workfare policies and ethnic minorities. Much less is said about how vulnerable ethnic minority groups are perceived in authoritarian neoliberal regimes. This paper contributes to a better understanding of how such regimes perceive minorities: the use of the categories of racialized or non-racialized, and deserving or undeserving minorities.

Introduction

The Fidesz-KDNP government, which came into power in 2010, had the intention to establish a radically new system, which it defined in opposition to the previous liberal democratic, rights-based regime. The governing coalition had a supermajority for four terms, which allowed it to proceed with all policy and political changes they intended to implement. The Prime Minister, Viktor Orbán, declared in 2014 that “the new state that we are constructing in Hungary is an illiberal state, a non-liberal state”.¹ Different terminologies are used to describe this system, depending on which aspect of it is emphasized. It is agreed that it is an illiberal system (Scheiring and Szombati, 2020; Fodor, 2022) with strong autocratic, authoritarian, populist, and neoliberal components (Scheiring, 2019; Stubb and Lendvai-Bainton, 2020; Szombati, 2021; Lendvai-Bainton and Szelewa, 2021).

A wide range of literature tackles questions like how illiberalism is related to workfare policies (Lakner and Tausz, 2016; Szikra and Öktem, 2023). These studies emphasize how illiberalism adopts neoliberal principles, including neoliberal workfare policies and how it combines them with cuts in social benefits and restrictions on social rights. Also, there are several research on workfare and the most disadvantaged ethnic minority, the Roma, that focus on the complex question of how they are integrated but also discriminated against in workfare schemes and what consequences the workfare ideology has for their social acceptance (Szóke, 2015; Kóczé and van Baar, 2020). These studies suggest that while workfare schemes employ Roma, because of their low level of education, they can only be involved in very low-prestige and low-paid work. The jobs are underpaid, but they satisfy the prejudiced sense of justice of the population that Roma are not welfare scroungers, but live on income from their paid jobs. It is, however, much less discussed how this vulnerable minority group is represented at the intersection of the different policy areas while they experience deep poverty and discrimination to a much larger degree than any other social group. Szikra (2018) argues that the Orbán government pursues a consistent ideology in its social and family policy. People with low incomes are often excluded from social benefits, and the symbolic divide created by the regime’s workfare policy between ‘workers’ and ‘non-workers’ reinforces this. Szikra does not analyze the ethnic dimension, but – based on the overlap between poverty, unemployment, and Roma ethnicity –, she notes the possibility that there is an ethnic dimension to class-based social exclusion.

On the other hand, despite the fact that social and family policies favor the middle and upper class while neglecting or punishing people with low incomes, studies show that people with lower income, education, and socio-economic status, including the Roma, are overrepresented among the supporters of the government (Róna *et al.*, 2020). It is not unprecedented for unprivileged, low-status minorities to support right-wing populist parties (Inglehart and Norris, 2016). In the case of the Hungarian Roma, this behavior is usually explained by a relative increase in living standards, despite the persistence of a stable social structure with little or no social mobility (Gerő *et al.*, 2020). The social, family, and work policies implemented by the regime are designed so that the most disadvantaged feel that they benefit from the system. Authoritarian populist strategies are used to obtain the support of the economically disadvantaged (Scheiring, 2019), and it is guaranteed that some part of the limited resources reaches the lower social strata, which form the majority of the government’s supporters (Róna *et al.*, 2020).

The other intriguing question concerns the political communication of illiberal, authoritarian, and populist regimes. Convincing, influencing, and mobilizing the population to sustain popular support is essential in their governing strategies. Using discriminatory, exclusionary language, scapegoating, and stereotyping certain social groups are among the communication tools these regimes use (Bocskor, 2018; Buzogány and Varga, 2018). Representation of the ‘undeserving poor/ethnic

minority,' as opposed to the 'deserving' dominant upper classes/ethnic group, is typical of their discourse (Czibere and Kovách, 2022).

In our paper, we aim to reveal to what extent this pattern is discernible in the case of the Hungarian illiberal regime and its communication about social, family and workfare policies vis-à-vis the Roma. In other words, this paper aims to shed light on how this illiberal and authoritarian system, which adopts neoliberal principles, refers to the Roma. This new system is built on the idea that income can only come from work; therefore, family allowances have been tied to employment, and social benefits have been radically reduced, all of which have serious effects on the most disadvantaged social groups, among whom Roma are overrepresented. Our analysis aims to explore how the Roma are represented in the discourses of the government. Are they seen as the undeserving racialized poor? Are they stigmatized and presented as a socially despised category – as Roma often appear in anti-liberal, far-right discourses? The paper seeks answers to these questions by focusing on the discourses used by the illiberal, neoliberal authoritarian regime concerning its ideological stance on workfare and social policies and their interesting implications for the Roma.

To understand the ideological embeddedness of policy discourses, we need to address the wider picture of what social policy means in this system and how the racialization of the Roma may be interpreted. The political aspect of the Orbán regime, which involves weakening the rule of law, democratic institutions, and a rights-based political community, can be understood as illiberalism. However, we are introducing other concepts that can better illuminate the regime's strategies and attitudes toward social, family, and work policies. Therefore, the paper starts with explaining the concepts of *authoritarian neoliberalism*, *punitive populism*, and *illiberal paternalism* (Lendvai-Bainton and Szelewa, 2021; Szombati, 2021). The concept of *postraciality* (Goldberg, 2015; Powell and van Baar, 2019) is used and explained to generate conceptual tools for understanding the representation of Roma in political discourses and the conclusions that can be drawn from this.

Then, social, family and workfare policies in the Hungarian authoritarian neoliberal and illiberal paternalist regime will be explored by focusing on the shift from a rights-based approach to a work-based system. The paper continues by analyzing government discourses between 2010 and 2023. It reveals how the government frames each policy area and how Roma fit into these frames. The policy frame analysis used in the research (Benford and Snow 2000; Smith, 2021) provides answers to the questions of what problems may be identified and how the Roma are involved (diagnostic framing), what solutions are suggested and how these affect both the Roma and the non-Roma population (prognostic framing), and how the majority and the Roma are motivated and mobilized to accept government messages (motivational framing). By exploring these dimensions in the discourses, a more refined picture of how Roma are perceived by the regime is created.

Conceptualizing the regime

Authoritarian neoliberalism

The term 'authoritarian neoliberalism' (Giroux, 2015; Lendvai-Bainton and Szelewa, 2021) is used to describe regimes with a strong socio-political authoritarian and neoliberal political orientation. The political aspect of the concept refers to the process of the weakening of democratic institutions (removing checks and balances, changing constitutional practices, etc.), while the social part refers to the rejection of social and human rights and social justice. The term 'neoliberalism' captures reforms

that reflect the idea of a competitive state and market society (Krastev and Holmes, 2019; Brown *et al.*, 2018).

Following these ideas, neoliberal authoritarian regimes are characterized by anti-welfarism. Social solidarity is emptied, and instead of social citizenship or a rights-based approach to social protection, work-based merit is a central concept. One deserves to be assisted only if one proves one's merits through work. This is the basic principle of workfarism (Lendvai-Bainton and Szelewa, 2021; Scheiring and Szombati, 2020). In such regimes, the most vulnerable often remain without protection. Among them, we typically find disadvantaged ethnic minorities (Szikra, 2018).

These regimes reject individual rights-claiming and center their politics on other entities and values, such as corporations, work, property, capital, families, churches, and whiteness. Governments are seen as controlling market developments; in this, they have the right and duty to discipline society (Lendvai-Bainton and Szelewa, 2021).

Punitive populism and illiberal paternalism

The ideological division of society between those who strive and work hard and those who depend on welfare benefits and get support without working has been an important component of neoliberal capitalism (Soss *et al.*, 2011). Punitive populism is also based on this idea. However, it also has a moral feature, which infers that a just society can be created by disciplining those who would live without working. “*Punitive populism calls for the establishment of a clear moral and legal hierarchy between ‘strivers’ and ‘scroungers’*” (Szombati, 2021: 1708).

Illiberal paternalism describes a set of policies and regime specificities which could be identified as a “*systemic drive to reinstate naturalised hierarchies with the selective provision of protection and care for those who conform with the state-sanctioned ideology of gainful work*” (Szombati, 2021: 1705). The punitive populist system seeks to discipline people with low incomes, whereas the illiberal paternalist one still wants to exercise control over this population; it does so through offering (public) work as a means of social acceptance. The system is illiberal because it intends to dismantle social rights while basing society on a naturalized hierarchy of race, ethnicity, gender, family status, and sexuality. Its paternalist aspect refers to the selective provisions for those who accept work as the basis of social membership. Participating in (public) work gives people with low incomes some degree of protection and recognition (Szombati, 2021). However, this kind of paternalism “*draws attention to the fact that illiberal statecraft is not confined to institutions and ideology but depends critically on interpersonal relations—more precisely, the imposed intimacies of patron-client relationships*” (Szombati, 2021: 1720). The public work or workfare program is essential in such illiberal regimes for pacifying ethnic relations and achieving a new social consensus based on work. The system is based on the neoliberal idea and value awarded to work and merit, and its paternalism is different in that it does not aim to produce good, self-governing citizens but rather people who comply with patron-client relationships.

Post-raciality

While the concepts presented above grasp various aspects of how vulnerable, poor, and ethnic populations are governed in regimes characterized by authoritarian, neoliberal, and illiberal features, we also need some further conceptualization concerning how racialization is manifest in these systems.

Historically, we can speak of different types of racisms and observe fluctuation between these types. Most commonly, the racism of exploitation and expulsion can be detected in racializing

societies. The racism of exploitation is based on the idea that racial groups have their marginalized and precarious place in society. The racism of expulsion holds that racial groups should be marginalized *from* society, as they have no social, cultural, political, or physical place in it (Goldberg, 2015; Powell and van Baar, 2019). These two forms often interact, and the same groups may suffer different forms of racism at the same time. According to recent conceptualizations, contemporary racisms must be understood in the context of the neoliberalization of societies. Wacquant (2009) describes how the securitization and penalization of racialized groups lead to the invisibilization of the social problems of these populations. Goldberg (2016) talks about ‘post-raciality’, where the constant visibilization and invisibilization of racial groups take place. At the same time, the structural conditions that reproduce inequalities have been rendered invisible by neoliberalism. Post-raciality is the denial of racism, both the structural causes of it and its historical legacy and how it continues to reproduce contemporary racism (Goldberg, 2009; De Lissovoy, 2012; Leonardo, 2009; Lipsitz, 2006).

It is argued (Powell and van Baar, 2019) that we can differentiate specific ‘regimes of visibility’ or visualization, particularly related to the strategy of securitization. Sometimes, the conditions are concealed, and the racial groups are invisibilized; at other times, they are made hyper-visible, primarily through criminalization and pathologization. The hyper-visibilization of the racial features of marginalized, precarious groups is re-emphasized while the conditions of their precariousness are invisibilized (Goldberg, 2015).

Since the structural conditions of inequality are concealed or rendered invisible, the affected populations are readily seen as responsible for their own status. This responsabilization is widely used by populist and nationalist leaders, who claim that marginalized groups are beneficiaries of preferential treatment to the detriment of the (white) majority (Powell and van Baar, 2019; Dunajeva and Kostka, 2022). It also follows that, according to the neoliberalist idea of social advancement based on the self-responsibility of the individual, one should be productive; otherwise, one does not deserve to enjoy the benefits of civic and human rights. In the same spirit, color-blind policies hide the real, structural causes of racial inequalities (Kostka, 2018; Dunajeva and Kostka, 2022).

The social and political context

Hungary is a post-communist country that gradually became illiberal in the early 2010s. The country’s largest ethnic minority group is the Roma, who make up around ten percent of the population and are overrepresented among the poor, the unemployed, and those with low or no formal education. They have historically faced discrimination and stereotyping, with common stereotypes depicting them as welfare-dependent and criminal (Vicsek, 1997; Bernáth and Messing 2013).

The 2008 economic crisis hit Hungary hard, and the socialist government in power then introduced radical austerity measures while it tried to maintain the safety net for low-income families and children (Inglot, 2020). A social crisis exacerbated the situation, involving rising unemployment and poverty and high levels of household indebtedness. The Orbán regime² came about as a response to a set of crises preceding the 2010s (Stubbs and Lendvai-Bainton, 2020; Lugosi, 2018). Hungary also experienced an intense political crisis in this period. It was the time of the rise and strengthening of the new far-right, Jobbik. The party’s primary political strategy was to divert the political agenda with radical and racist ideas. They started to use a strong anti-Roma political narrative. Roma were criminalized and blamed for their welfare dependency to an unprecedented degree, a stance implicitly or explicitly shared by mainstream political actors, including the moderate right-wing, left-wing and liberal side (Karácsony and Róna, 2011; Feischmidt *et al.*, 2013). This resulted in the implementation

of various punitive social policy measures by the Socialist government. Public work programs were expanded, and participation was made compulsory for the poor to qualify for social protection (Lendvai-Bainton and Szelewa, 2021). The right-wing Fidesz-KDNP government, which took power in 2010 with Viktor Orbán as the prime minister, continued this policy and built a new system based on the idea of anti-welfarism and workfare.

When entering power, the new parliament declared the creation of a ‘National Cooperation System.’ This was a symbolic act involving laying the foundations of a new political community formed by a ‘social contract.’ It was based on principles that fundamentally reject liberal democratic conceptions and replace them with an illiberal, majoritarian system (Majtényi and Majtényi, 2016). The authoritarian regime wanted to put an end to ‘individual rights’ and ‘rights-based approaches,’ and the welfare state in its previous form, as also stipulated in the new constitution (Majtényi and Majtényi, 2016). The government emphasized anti-welfareism, the principle of self-responsibility and the idea of a merit-based society (Lendvai-Bainton and Szelewa, 2021). The end of the welfare state and the coming of workfare went along with the marginalization of certain social groups by creating insider-outsider binaries and labeling groups deserving or undeserving (Stubbs and Lendvai-Bainton, 2020).

Cash benefits and other social assistance schemes were cut significantly (Lugosi, 2018; Szikra, 2018) and the duration of unemployment benefit was reduced from nine to three months (Köllő, 2019). For the unemployed and the low-skilled, public work schemes were extended. The policy expectation was that people in the public work scheme would find employment in the primary labor market once their personal or economic situation improved. While such schemes existed before 2010, the program was expanded significantly by the government; in 2010, the scheme provided 53 thousand jobs, and in 2015, 208 thousand.

Rolling back social benefits and making public work compulsory meant that opting out involved remaining without an income (Fodor, 2022). There are many reasons why public work as a policy instrument is considered problematic. In disadvantaged regions, there are not enough jobs, and jobs for the unskilled or the low-educated are not available, and public work is often the only employment. Public work schemes, however, involve underpaid work, and reinforce patron-client relations (Vidra, 2018).

While public work initially had a strong punitive character, throughout the 2010s, it became less of a disciplinary policy than a means of protection and recognition for participants. This shift was an essential political tool and strategy of the regime as it contributed to pacifying the ethnic tensions in rural Hungary by inserting people experiencing poverty and the Roma into work, thereby diminishing the anger and frustration of the majority population who believed in the myth of the over-subsidized welfare dependency of marginalized groups. This transformation from punitive public work to paternalist suggested that the poor/Roma are entitled to some protection, dignity, and membership in the community through work. However, as the most vulnerable are deprived of basic social and human rights protection, they become dependent on those who provide work: the patron, be this the local mayor or political leaders (Szombati, 2021).

The illiberal, neoliberal authoritarian regime also defined one of its primary goals as the demographic renewal of the country. This was, nonetheless, embedded in its selective social investment strategy (Cook *et al.*, 2023) as it involved supporting fertility among middle- and high-income families. The related policy was introduced under the name of ‘family protection’ measures aimed at increasing birth rates. Following the principle of the work-based society, policies designed to help families are employment-based. For example, one of the first measures of the government was to introduce a flat personal income tax of 16%, then reduced to 15%. Other measures included tax-credit-

based benefits, earned income tax credits, subsidized mortgages and loans, and ‘baby loans’ (Lugosi, 2018; Szikra, 2014). Importantly, those employed in public work could not benefit from most of the measures (Szikra, 2018) because of the low level of salaries. At the same time, cash benefits for people with low incomes and the universal family allowance were frozen at the level of 2008. Thus, benefits that target the most vulnerable (both means-tested and citizenship-based) represent a small and shrinking proportion of all family benefits. Accordingly, family policies with pro-natalist goals provide various forms of support for families in which parents have ‘proper’ employment and at least an average or high income (Fodor, 2022).

The foundations of the treatment of the Roma minority under the illiberal, authoritarian system have been laid out in the new constitution named the Fundamental Law. One crucial aspect concerning the Roma is that the latter declares that Hungary is one (ethnic) nation, the only subject of the constitution. Any notion of multiculturalism is refused. National minorities, including the Roma, are recognized but do “*not participate in the sovereign power of the people*” (Majtényi and Majtényi, 2016: 191), in contrast to what the previous constitution stipulated. Some even claim that this renders them secondary citizens. The Fundamental Law also declares that equal opportunities are promoted. However, new terminology is used to describe how this should be achieved. Instead of the previously applied terminology ‘upgrading,’ implying systemic changes, the word ‘catching up’ is used to refer to the individual’s responsibility for successful integration. It suggests that integration is not the responsibility of the state, but the result of individual efforts. Furthermore, the Fundamental Law also stipulates self-responsibility through work: “*Everyone shall be obliged to contribute to the enrichment of the community through his or her work, in accordance with his or her abilities and possibilities*” (Majtényi and Majtényi, 2016: 195).

Methodology

The research used three data sources: pro-government media articles, state-of-the-nation address speeches, and the 2010 Fidesz-KDNP party manifesto. The timeframe of the analysis was between 1 April 2010 and 30 July 2023. May 2010 was when the illiberal government came into power, and 2023 was its fourth cycle. The final dataset consisted of 75 documents.

Regarding pro-government media articles, we searched for communications from government politicians, ministries, ministers, and state secretaries. The media chosen for analysis is one of the outlets loyal to the incumbent party, *Magyar Nemzet*. This was used as a source between 2010 and 2015 and 2019 and 2023, as it had an independent phase between 2015 and 2019. For 2015 and 2018, a short-lived outlet, *Magyar Idők*, was used to substitute for *Magyar Nemzet*. We used the following search terms: *social, work, workfare, and family (policy)+Roma; Roma catch up/scaling up/integration (felzárkóztatás/integráció)*. The final article dataset after cleaning contained 63 articles (a surprisingly small number given the length of the period). The articles were further broken down into utterances by different speakers.

State-of-the-nation address speeches are annual public speeches in which the Prime Minister, Viktor Orbán, evaluates the previous year and typically also discusses the goals, prospects, and challenges of the future. These speeches are always held in February in front of a selected pro-government audience, broadcast by numerous media channels, and are available online as written text. In 2021, the speech was canceled due to the COVID-19 pandemic, which left us with twelve documents from 2011 to 2023.

The third type of data source was the party manifesto of Fidesz-KDNP from 2010, written before the party came to power. This is the only party manifesto available in the given period; the ruling party did not publish a party manifesto in any following election year until 2023.

The data were thematically coded, and we deployed the policy frame analysis method, based on the works of Benford and Snow (2000) and Smith (2021), to categorize content into different frames: *diagnostic*, *prognostic*, and *motivational*. The *diagnostic framing* refers to the identification of the problem, the causes and consequences, and the attribution of blame. *Prognostic framing* suggests solutions to problems and identifies strategies and actions. Last, *motivational framing* provides incentives for action and, through the presentation of the positive results of policies, is used to convince and mobilize people.

Frame analysis: Roma in ‘work-based’ society

Diagnostic framing: what is the problem and who is to be blamed?

The authoritarian neoliberal idea of anti-welfarism and the rejection of individual and social rights (Stubbs and Lendvai-Bainton, 2020; Lendvai-Bainton and Szelewa, 2021) appears in the diagnosis of the challenges the new political elite has to tackle. Inactivity and unemployment are identified as the major causes of the social, political, and economic crisis of the early 2010s. More specifically, the previous government’s leftist welfare and poverty policies are blamed for making the poor welfare dependent: “*The [previous] government [...] prioritised high levels of welfare rather than decent income*” (Fidesz-KDNP party manifesto 2010: 72).

The claim is that the rights-based leftist poverty policies are also responsible for turning the Roma into passive victims by giving them undeserved social benefits with no expectation of work. Thus, the main responsibility lies not with the Roma but with the previous administration according to the discourse. The leftist-liberal discourse’s focus on individual human rights prevents Roma from being seen as anything other than victims. The result has been more conflict, hate crimes, and a lack of social peace and integration. “*The Socialists have created antipathy and hatred towards the Roma with their completely flawed social policy*” (Fidesz-KDNP party manifesto 2010: 81).

While in the discourse the blame is put primarily on leftist welfare policies, there is also the punitive approach (Soss *et al.*, 2011) of making a moral distinction between those who cannot find work and those who have no intention of working and would rather live on social benefits, turn to criminal behavior, or combine these two: “*It would be a big mistake to equate those who want to work, but cannot get a job, and those who could work, but think that living on welfare or other state benefits is still more comfortable, and besides, you can make money from this and that. If nothing else, from chicken theft*” (PM, State-of-the-nation address, 2011).

Criminal behavior and living on social benefits are intertwined and often put on the same page in this narrative: “*It will not be possible to make a living from crime [...] nor from welfare*” (PM, MN, 23 July 2012). Threatening language is used towards those who try to live a life based on benefits and crime: “*If you try to do that, you will be out of luck*” (PM, MN, 23 July 2012). Moreover, “*We supported those who were living for their children [...], but we were neither understanding nor lenient towards those who wanted to live not for their children but from their children*” (PM, State-of-the-nation address, 2019).

The reference to petty crimes – “chicken theft” (PM, State-of-the-nation address, 2011) – and “living from their children” (PM, State-of-the-nation address, 2019) can be interpreted as coded racism, as having lots of children for the sake of social benefits, and being engaged in petty crimes (especially stealing) are common racist stereotypes (Stewart, 2012). However, in most of the government narratives, the poverty of the Roma is not racialized but explained by the fact that there is no work-based income in many Roma families: “*More than half of Roma households have no working members, and in a third of them only one person has a work-based income*” (MN 16 June 2011).

Prognostic framing: what should be done?

Based on the government’s diagnosis that all social problems are the fault of the former left-wing political elite and rights-based ideology, a new set of values has been created as a solution, embodied in the concept of a ‘work-based society.’ The neoliberal idea of work-based merit (Stubbs and Lendvai-Bainton, 2020) is emphasized, while the importance of work becomes absolutized: “*If there is work, there is everything – if there is no work, there is nothing*” (Fidesz-KDNP party manifesto 2010, 40). Work is framed both as the “*basis for human dignity*” (PM, State-of-the-nation address, 2014) on the individual level, as well as a basis for the construction of the collective identity (‘us’) on the societal level: “*Work is the basis for the security, autonomy, and independence of every human being. [...] Work gives us sustenance, pride, and a sense of belonging to the community: in the family, in the home, at work, among friends*” (Fidesz-KDNP party manifesto 2010, 20).

The authoritarian neoliberal approach implies that a work-based society is achieved by putting the inactive to work while minimizing social benefits (Szikra, 2018). The Prime Minister makes it clear that: “*Hungarians will not receive income support in the long term*” (PM, MN, 23 July 2012).

Both the neoliberal concept of work-based merit (Stubbs and Lendvai-Bainton, 2020) and the punitive populist idea of making a moral difference between ‘strivers’ and ‘scroungers’ and proposing to punish those who are morally unfit (Szombati, 2021) appear in the discourse. While there is constant criminalization of the welfare-dependent poor, there is no direct racial reference to the Roma. The goal is ostensibly to overcome the wrongs and shortcomings of the leftist-liberal governments created by rights-based, social rights, and welfare policies. The Roma are included in the discourse but not directly identified with the scroungers. Instead, they are offered a ‘social contract,’ the same as is offered to all Hungarian people. This social contract, or “‘*mini-constitution*’ between the government of Hungary and its legitimate Roma political class,” refers to “*the mutual expectations and commitments of the state, the Roma community and the majority society, [...] and define[s] the rights and obligations of both the state and the representatives of the Roma community for social inclusion*” (MN, 30 May 2011).

The basic obligation is to eschew welfare dependency (and criminality) and to be committed to work. The neoliberal idea of self-responsibilization (Powell and van Baar, 2019) is emphasized when claiming that the previous administration, which gave social benefits instead of work, “*did not consider them humans*” (PM, State-of-the-nation address, 2019). Fidesz-KDNP urges society to see that the Roma are not passive victims but capable and valuable resources, a labor-market reserve, and desperately needed to overcome the crisis and achieve the country’s total economic potential. “*In order to have 5-5.5 million working, tax-*

paying citizens in Hungary, the Roma must also work” (PM, MN, 23 July 2012). The narrative also claims that, unlike by the previous administration, Roma are seen as equal partners: “*None of them [previous leftist governments] dared to embark on the modernization of the structure, and none of them treated the Roma as a meaningful partner*” (Political analyst, MN, 30 May 2011).

Motivational framing: narratives involving the positive results of Roma-related policies

While the moralizing punitive concept is part of the discourse, through the neoliberal self-responsibilization applied to the Roma, a new type of social acceptance is formulated. This is based on the illiberal paternalist idea (Szombati, 2021), whereby the state offers opportunities – (public) employment – and seals it with a social contract, promising solidarity, recognition, and acceptance in return.

The propagandistic narrative of the government involves constructing positive messages about their policies to mobilize their constituency to keep supporting their efforts at governing. This motivational framing suggests that everyone is benefiting from the proposed policies. Integrating the Roma into the labor market would be beneficial for both the Roma themselves and the non-Roma majority, as Roma would no longer be welfare-dependent but valuable members of society, contributing to the country’s economic growth with their work.

For this, it is first and foremost the unemployed who have to be motivated and convinced to accept the offer of the new government to engage in productive work. The Prime Minister acts like a strict but well-intentioned teacher or father figure, using paternalistic language, promising “recognition for work” and “punishment for breaking the law” (PM, State-of-the-nation speech, 2011): “*Not all people on income support feel that they need to return to work. [...] what we need here is not condemnation, scolding or lecturing, but patience, empathy, and gentle persistence*” (PM, State of-the-nation address, 2012). Those who accept the offer are invited to join the community: “*Those who work for it deserve to share in its success. Individual freedom, but shared responsibility. Common work, common success*” (PM, State-of-the-nation address, 2013).

This new offer is part of the illiberal paternalist strategy (Szombati, 2021), which allows Roma to leave behind the undeserving category of ‘them’ and become members of the category of ‘us’ by returning to the labor market. In the success narrative of the government, the Roma have recognized the opportunity and taken it; in other words, they accepted the call for self-responsibilization: “*Roma communities have joined the work-based society. [...] more Roma are working nowadays than ever before*” (Roma MP, MN, 07 May 2022). The Prime Minister repeatedly praises the Roma who have joined the work-based society: “*It is impossible to speak without emotion about the great change that tens of thousands of Gypsy families have taken up the jobs offered [them]; [...] They are living from work instead of benefits, raising their children properly, and they have earned the respect of us all*” (PM, State-of-the-nation address, 2020).

As a result of behaving according to the expectations of a work-based society, social conflicts between Roma and non-Roma have disappeared according to the government’s discourse. Not only has the government succeeded in reducing crime, but it has also achieved the goal of social inclusion and united the nation: “*After the 2010 elections, radical changes and policy processes were initiated, as a result of which peaceful coexistence became the*

hallmark of Hungarian society. There are meeting points, people respect each other and recognise each other's achievements. Communities have been created and strengthened that did not exist before 2010” (MN, 07 May 2022).

Besides joining the symbolic body of the nation, Roma may objectively improve their situation. *“Data show that poverty indicators among the Roma population have improved, and their income and housing conditions are better than before.”* (MN 22 May 2023). Roma integration (‘scaling up’) is narrated as a total success.

In the discourse, consequently, the Roma feel content in this new system: *“Two-thirds of them feel particularly happy. In their identity, in addition to the family, their belonging to the Hungarian nation is also decisive.* (MN 07 April 2022). It is highlighted in government discourse, The satisfaction of the Roma population is manifested in concrete electoral behavior: *“They supported the national side because they recognized the government's efforts to create a work-based society”* (Roma MP, MN 07 May 2022). Roma’s overrepresentation among the voters of Fidesz-KDNP is supported by independent research as well (Róna *et al.*, 2020).

Discussion: The in/visibilization of Roma under the authoritarian neoliberal and illiberal system

In the previous section, we explored how the political narrative in the authoritarian neoliberal and illiberal paternalist system identifies problems, on whom it puts the blame and to whom it allocates responsibility, how it utilizes the neoliberal idea of self-responsibilization and productivity, what work-based and merit-based society it envisions, and what paternalism brings to the system. Discourses about policy-related narratives were studied by focusing on the Roma minority. We conclude that the main narrative changes over the years, and while it was racially coded at the beginning, it became nonracializing but paternalistic. Digging deeper into understanding the ‘Roma narrative’ under neoliberal and illiberal paternalist conditions, we apply the theory of post-raciality. These theories conceptualize ‘visibilization’ and ‘invisibilization,’ the latter which refers to the process of concealing the structural causes of social and racial inequalities. The concept of self-responsibilization is one of the means by which these causes could be made invisible. At the same time, racial groups themselves may be either invisibilized or visibilized/hyper-visibilized. Criminalization is a typical means of making racial/ethnic groups hyper-visible (Wacquant, 2009; Goldberg, 2015; Powell and van Baar, 2019).

The invisibilization of the causes of inequalities leading to exclusion and discrimination against the Roma is one of the founding principles of the regime. In the government discourse, the primary cause of all problems concerning the Roma and ethnic relations is identified in the leftist-liberal rights-based welfare and social policies, which have made Roma inactive and welfare-dependent. In reality, Roma are overrepresented among both the unskilled and low-educated and live in disadvantaged regions where there are no jobs or not enough jobs, plus they also face educational and work-related discrimination. These are the main structural factors behind their high unemployment and inactivity rates (Rostás and Kovács, 2021). The discourse fails to mention these structural roots of ethnic inequalities and undermines the validity of racial discrimination by refuting the rights-based approach.

The results of the implemented policies are discussed in a very optimistic and positive tone in the government narratives, while all of them conceal the real problems and structural conditions. The regime has offered a social contract to the whole population and the Roma

based on the idea of self-responsibilization. Engaging in productive work and not relying on benefits will make one part of the national community, regardless of ethnic background. The idea of self-responsibilization invisibilizes the structural problems behind inactivity (Powell and van Baar, 2019). The social contract with the Roma is narrated as a success story of self-responsibility in which most of the Roma have accepted the offer, live productive lives, and thus became full members of the national community.

The invisibilization of structural conditions also leads to the invisibilization of the evidence of how these policies work. This can be grasped by looking at some of the data on Roma employment. Data show that in the 2010s, due to the economic boom, the country experienced shortages in the workforce that resulted in the labor market absorbing a lot of previously inactive people, including the Roma. Employment rates have increased most among the least educated social groups since 2010. However, inequalities between Roma and non-Roma have not changed. In 2015, 20% of Roma men were employed and 10% of Roma women (Lugosi, 2018), while in 2022, the employment rate (aged 20-64) of Roma men was 44% and 23% of Roma women, whereas it was 81% for non-Roma men and 65% for non-Roma women (Fodor, 2022).

While their overall employment rate has increased, their employment situation is still significantly worse than that of the general population (Bereményi, 2023). Public work schemes provide work for those who cannot find jobs in the primary labor market. However, this employment does not entitle them to many of the family policy benefits eligible to employed people. These benefits are salary-based and can only be claimed above a certain income level. (tax credit, baby loan, etc.) While it is true that not only higher-status families benefited from the newly introduced measures, but lower-class ones, too (Fodor, 2022), including Roma, their eligibility for benefits related to family policies is limited due to the lack of ‘real’ employment and their disproportionate participation in public work (Roma Civil Monitor, 2022).

In the official discourse, a further success related to the social contract is the social and ethnic peace achieved through rolling back social benefits and making people with low incomes and the Roma work. This pacification of ethnic conflicts can also be seen as an example of the invisibilization of certain structural conditions. As mentioned, the social contract and the work-based approaches may be interpreted as a means of illiberal paternalism (Szombati, 2021). Work, often public work, is offered to the inactive poor, but this reinforces the patron-client relationship. In other words, the price of ethnic peace for the Roma and people with low incomes is the acceptance of the ‘unjust’ system of voluntary subordination.

Through work, poverty is also claimed in the discourse to have been reduced for both the whole population and the Roma. Employment is indeed a crucial factor in poverty alleviation, and there has been an increase in employment rates, including those of the Roma. However, the complex structural factors behind poverty are well concealed. The claim that “*[t]he number of people at risk of poverty fell by 930,000 between 2012 and 2018 [and t]he number of people living in extreme poverty fell from 500,000 in 2012 to 386,000 in 2016*” (State Secretary, MI, 09 June 2018) is highly misleading. Hungary is among the poorest countries in the EU; about 2.5-2.8 million people out of the population of 10 million are considered to be living in poverty. The European indicator AROPE (At Risk of Poverty or Social Exclusion), which the government likes to refer to, indicates that the poverty level is lower than in Sweden, Austria, and Luxembourg, countries that are more developed and richer than Hungary. The explanation is simply because these indicators measure social differences rather than poverty (Egyensúly, 2021).

The goal of invisibilisation can be seen in the success of the illiberal paternalistic strategy. As a result of the work and merit-based policies, a relative improvement in their living conditions has become a general experience of the Roma population (Egyensúly, 2021). According to the government narrative, Roma feel content and happy under this system, and it is even said by Roma politicians that it is because of the recognition and protection offered by the ‘social contract’ that they support the regime. Structural invisibilization is another successful strategy by which the system can maintain its electoral support.

Whether and how Roma are categorized is also crucial to their invisibilization or hyper-visibility in official discourses. In fact, we see both strategies. The punitive populist reasoning is present when mention is made of the need to eliminate welfare support and social benefits. It makes those who want to live on benefits highly visible by criminalizing them and promising to punish such behavior. It is also mentioned in relation to those who live “*from their children*.” However, we could identify only a few indirect or coded references to the Roma in connection with ‘scroungers,’ typically at the beginning of the period of analysis, which gradually disappear from the discourse, and a more paternalistic tone takes over.

Deploying the ‘social contract’ approach and what it infers, self-responsibility and productivity, is intended to invisibilize the Roma. By accepting the social contract, Roma can overcome their stigmatized identity. This new offer is part of the illiberal paternalist strategy, which allows them to leave behind the undeserving category of ‘them.’ Along with the invisibilization of the stigmatized Roma category, under the authoritarian neoliberal system, those who do not accept the offer (because they are among the most vulnerable) will not only be unprotected but cannot be part of the national community and cannot even be talked about. Thus, those Roma who fail to become active and productive and benefit from the family policies and those who still live in segregated communities and deep poverty are invisibilized in the regime’s discourse.

Conclusions

In our paper, we describe what social, family, and work(fare) policies are introduced in authoritarian, neoliberal, populist, and illiberal systems and how the disadvantaged Roma ethnic minority is portrayed in official discourse. Our assumption was that in systems that shift from rights-based ones to work- and merit-based societies, ethnic minorities are often criminalized and stigmatized as being welfare-dependent and undeserving. Using qualitative frame analysis, we aimed to reveal to what extent Roma are blamed and eventually racialized by such a system.

Employing the concept of neoliberal authoritarianism, we claimed that social and family policies became almost totally merit-based, thus only those who contribute to the productivity of the society ‘deserve’ to be supported (Szikra, 2018; Lendvai-Bainton and Szelewa, 2021).

The concepts of punitive populism and illiberal paternalism (Szombati, 2021) highlight how the ‘deserving’ and the ‘undeserving’ poor have been represented. In fact, one of the major findings of our analysis of government discourses on policies is that the dividing line between ‘strivers and scroungers’ is based on merit (participation in productivity). Those Roma who become self-responsible and participate in productivity are praised for their efforts and welcomed as part of the national community. It was revealed that except for some instances of

coded racism at the beginning of the 2010s, no open racialization of Roma, including blaming them for welfare dependency and criminalization, characterized the discourse. The fact that explicit racism disappeared from government discourse and the narrative took on a more conciliatory, paternalistic tone may also have contributed to the Roma support for the governing party.

Using the theory of post-raciality, and within these, the concepts of visibilization and invisibilization (Goldberg, 2009; Powell and van Baar, 2019; de Lissovoy, 2012; Leonardo, 2009; Lipsitz, 2006; Goldberg, 2015), we interpreted our findings regarding how Roma were perceived in official narratives. The most important conclusion is that by relying on the merit-based, self-responsibilization approach and refusing a rights-based one, the structural causes of ethnic inequalities have been successfully concealed. The official discourse invisibilizes all problems that may underlie the poverty and social exclusion of the Roma and puts the responsibility on individual efforts. In the same vein, those Roma who could not or 'did not want to' participate in productive society and did not accept the 'social contract' were also invisibilized; they were not part of the official narrative.

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¹ Prime Minister Viktor Orbán’s Speech at the 25th Bálványos Summer Free University and Student Camp <https://2015-2019.kormany.hu/en/the-prime-minister/the-prime-minister-s-speeches/prime-minister-viktor-orban-s-speech-at-the-25th-balvanyos-summer-free-university-and-student-camp>

² The “Orbán regime” refers to the coalition government of the Young Democrats (Fidesz), and the Christian Democrats (KDNP). Viktor Orbán is the founding member, the president and the MP of Fidesz.